

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Teacher Education Students' Perceptions on the Implementation of the Drop Everything And Read (DEAR) Program

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the perceptions of the *Drop Everything And Read* (DEAR) Program among the Teacher Education students of San Isidro College. It examined the opinions of the Teacher Education students on the DEAR program and its objectives as well as their views of themselves as readers. It also determined the reading preferences and the perceptions of the Teacher Education students on their comprehension and vocabulary skills.

The study used the researcher-made questions for the perceptions of the students of the DEAR Program based on the variables of the study. A language expert professor validated the questions used in the FGD. These questions were pilot-tested to 10 Teacher Education students. It employed a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) among the 25 randomly chosen Teacher Education students which constitute 20% of the total enrolment of the School of Education (SED) who took Bachelor of Secondary Education and Bachelor of Elementary Education.

Findings revealed that the perceptions of the respondents on the implementation of the DEAR Program have a positive impact to the students and were helpful to them. The students considered the DEAR Program as a tool for learning. The Program improved their reading and writing skills. The reading preferences of the student were mostly newspapers, magazines and the Readers' Digest. The DEAR program helped all the students in their vocabulary and comprehension skills.

Key words: *Teacher Education Students, Perceptions. Drop Everything and Read*

INTRODUCTION

The demands for students who have good reading abilities are indispensable in the present day educational milieu. Everyday new information and new knowledge pours in. Reading has become an essential part of the modern day society. It is read-or-be-left-out race. There is no denying to the fact that the world now is very complex especially because of the presence of technology. But a considerable number of researchers and authors would agree of the fact that reading is the focal point of every student's academic endeavor. It is always the baseline towards one's academic success.

The School of Education (SED) of San Isidro College (SIC) has its DEAR program which was launched during the Academic Year 2010-2011. This is a program designed for the purpose of enhancing the reading skills among the teacher education students of SIC. The students were grouped into clusters in which each cluster was given designated time to go to the SED office and read. Hence, this program will require students to put significant time and effort to read an article after which they are to accomplish the reading logs for each reading task that they have done.

DEAR stands for “*Drop Everything and Read*”, founded by Beverly Cleary which is designed to remind folks of all ages to make reading a priority activity in their lives. The goal of the program is to prompt people to make reading a regular part of their routine, whether they are reading solo or together with their classmates, parents, or friends.

The opening question given by Wilson Lee Flores in his article written in *The Philippine Star* (2016), stated: “*What is one good habit we should learn from many of the world’s wealthiest and most successful entrepreneurs and professionals like Bill Gates, Facebook founder Mark Zuckerberg, and tech tycoon Elon Musk?*” According to him, it is reading---reading books, newspapers, magazines and internet articles.

Reading is undoubtedly a prerequisite of all habits one should acquire or do. It is in reading where you can learn a lot of things and a vehicle towards achieving success in every endeavor. According to Bridges (2015) “*reading shapes lives; even saves lives. Consider the stories of our greatest leaders across time, culture, and place. Almost all credit reading as an essential force that catapulted them to success*”.

John Coleman of Harvard Business Review said that reading can make you a better communicator and more empathetic. It is because, “*if one read a lot, one can share sensible things and discuss points comprehensively with colleagues, friends or classmates during gatherings or meetings.*”

In college, a considerable number of reading tasks are given by instructors to the students to do. To mention, students are tasked to do story analysis, home reading report, story summary, read short story, autobiography, current events, and so on. These tasks require a student to read a lot in order to discuss comprehensively the analysis that ought to be done in that particular text or story.

New York-based novelist and nationalist activist Ninotchka Rosca stressed in her talk during the launching of her three books here in the Philippines on February 28 that, all aspiring writers should keep reading a lot of books---that is one important key to success. She encouraged also business people and professionals to also read literature such as novels, books of short stories and poetry to enrich our minds and spirits (Philippine Star, 2016).

What is needed is a more complete picture of how students perceive the DEAR program of the school. This expanded knowledge on the results of the study might prompt exploration of the possibilities to create a whole school rich in reading culture. The DEAR Program of SIC has been implemented since July of the Academic Year 2010-2011. Since then no study has been done as to the issues and impacts of the program. It is the vision of the SED to inspire students to read more, to encourage them to share their enjoyment of reading with others and to celebrate the difference that reading makes among people, because everything changes when a person reads.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study determined the perceptions on the DEAR Program among the Teacher Education students of SIC. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the perceptions of the students on the following:
 - 1.1 DEAR Program and its objectives; and
 - 1.2 students themselves as readers?
2. What are the reading preferences of the Teacher Education students?
3. What are the perceptions of the students on the advantages and disadvantages of the DEAR Program?
4. What are the perceptions of the students on the significance of the DEAR program in their:
 - 4.1. Reading and Writing skills; and
 - 4.2. Vocabulary and Comprehension Skills?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The present study is anchored on the principle and concept of Anne Cunningham, renowned cognitive psychologist at University of California, Berkeley, which explains that reading is a “very rich, complex, and cognitive act” (2003 as cited by Bridges, 2015). It offers an immense opportunity to exercise our intelligence in ways we lose if we do not read. Hundreds of correlated studies demonstrate that the most successful students read the most, while those who struggle read the least.

These correlated studies suggest that the more our students read, the better their comprehension, vocabulary and fluency—and the more likely they are to build a robust knowledge of the world. In short, reading provides us with a cognitive workout that transcends not only our inherent abstract problem-solving abilities, but also our levels of education. Reading makes people smart.

Several studies have proved the impact of reading to one's life especially towards academic endeavor and success. The present study is anchored on the principles and concepts as viewed by various language experts, educators and researchers.

According to Lai, Tung & Luo (n.d.) in their study on the theory of reading strategies and its application by EFL learners, students have a need for gaining knowledge through reading because reading is a fundamental and critical skill for students to achieve academic success. If students cannot read well, the door towards the path of learning will most often be closed before them.

Reading is undoubtedly a prerequisite of all habits one should acquire or do. It is in reading where one can learn a lot of things, and a vehicle towards achieving success in every endeavor. As Bridges in 2015 points out that reading shapes lives; even saves lives. Consider the stories of our greatest leaders across time, culture, and place. Almost all credit reading as an essential force that catapulted them to success. Reading is the act of getting meaning from printed or written words, which is the basis for learning and one of the most important skills in everyday life (Owusu-Acheaw, 2014).

Vogel (2013) conducted an experimental study on the Impact of the READ 180. This READ 180 was a comprehensive reading intervention program for struggling readers designed to improve both their motivation to read and comprehension skills. The study determined the impact of READ 180 on the affective and cognitive reading skills with the various types of students placed into the READ 180 program. The findings for this study indicated that READ 180 was a beneficial intervention in limited areas for many at-risk high school students, but it did not meet the myriad of affective and cognitive needs required to grade level literacy development.

Slavin, Cheung, Groff & Lake (2008) conducted a study that reviewed research on middle and high

school reading programs, applying consistent methodological standards. This review was intended both to provide fair comparisons among the achievement effects of the full range approaches available to educators and policy makers and to summarize the current state of the art secondary reading programs. The scope of the review comprised of all the types of programs that teachers, principals, and superintendents might consider as a means of solving their secondary students' reading problems.

It is common knowledge that the best way to help students succeed is to encourage them to read. To that end, as educators, they want the students to discover themselves as readers, to have a sense of their own unique, rich, and wondrous reading lives.

Guthrie, Benneth & McGough (2007 as cited by Owusu-Acheaw in 2014) believe that "reading" is the act of getting meaning from printed or written words, which is the basis for learning and one of the most important skills in everyday life. Reading is usually associated with books as only the written words provide a complete picture of the act of reading. It means that through reading, the individual is able to build and fix things, enjoy stories, discover what others believe and develop ideas or beliefs of their own. Thus, reading provides the key to all forms of information necessary for the day to day survival and growth.

Chaudry and Low (2009) conducted a study on reading preferences among different generations where the respondents were asked to indicate three most preferred types of reading material in either print or electronic form. This study revealed significant findings that more than 70% of the participants favored newspapers as their top three reading sources. Internet and websites were second on the list, followed closely by fiction and print magazines. Electronic news and magazines paled against their print counterparts. Participants appeared to be more comfortable and familiar with paper, layout and structure of traditional print publications instead of reading off screens. Subsequently, they preferred print counterparts when it comes to news and magazines.

Hussain & Munshi (2011) conducted a study on *Identifying Reading Preferences of Secondary School Students* and found out that secondary school students preferred to read books, magazines, poetry and other

reading material to get pleasure through “edutainment”, kill their leisure time during holidays and/or weekends and for their emotional gratification. The respondents preferred to read books on religion, literature, novels, magazines and story and romantic books. Respondents were keen on reading newspaper, travelling story and scientific books, autobiographies and literature poetry and drama. However, they faced problems in reading and setting their reading preferences like high costs of books, context and circumstances, availability of books, time and their time management ability, examination and academic workload, lack of guidance, personal interest, and their study circles or groups.

It seems almost impossible to overstate the power of words; they literally have changed and will continue to change the course of world history. Perhaps the greatest tools we can give students for succeeding, not only in their education but more generally in life, is a large, rich vocabulary and the skills for using those words. Our ability to function in today’s complex social and economic worlds is mightily affected by our language skills and word knowledge (Pikulski & Templeton, 2004)

In addition to the vital importance of vocabulary for success in life, a large vocabulary is more specifically predictive and reflective of high levels of reading achievement. The Report of the National Reading Panel in 2000 for example concluded, “The importance of vocabulary knowledge has long been recognized in the development of reading skills. As early as 1924, researchers noted that growth in reading power relies on continuous growth in word knowledge” (Llach, 2009)

The relevance of reading as an activity leading to vocabulary acquisition cannot be denied, though. On the one hand, it provides learners with multiple exposures to words (Llach, 2009). Words are the tools we use to access our background knowledge, express ideas, and learn about new concepts. Students’ word knowledge is linked strongly to academic success. Specifically, word knowledge is crucial to reading comprehension, and determines how well students will be able to comprehend the texts they read in the upper elementary grades, in middle and high school, and in college. Moreover, words are the very foundation of learning. Finding ways to increase students’ vocabulary growth throughout the school years must become a major educational priority.

Winter-Hebert in her article “10 Benefits of Reading: Why You Should Read Every Day”, pointed out that “the more you read, the more words you gain exposure to, and they will inevitably make their way into your everyday vocabulary”. Being articulate and well-spoken is of great help in any profession, and knowing that you can speak to higher ups with self-confidence can be as enormous boost to your self-esteem. It could even aid in your career, as those who are well-read, well-spoken and knowledgeable on a variety of topics tend to get promotions more quickly than those with smaller vocabularies and lack of awareness of literature, scientific breakthroughs, and global events. Reading books is vital for learning new languages, as non-native speakers, gain exposure to words used in context, which will ameliorate their own speaking and writing fluency.

Reading comprehension is commonly known as an interactive mental process between reader’s linguistic knowledge, knowledge of the world, and knowledge about a given topic (Rahmani & Sadeghi, 2011). While reading, the reader constructs various representations of the text that are important for comprehension. Reading is essential for successfully completing all college-level courses. In other words, college students who are more proficient readers are most likely to experience more success in their courses.

Comprehension is understanding what is being said or read. When it comes to reading, it is an active process that must be developed if a learner is to become a proficient reader. Effective reading skill development is further accomplished when the learner becomes proficient in literal, inferential and critical comprehensive reading. A student’s academic progress is profoundly shaped by the ability to understand what they read are likely to acquire the skills necessary to participate in the 21st century workforce. Reading comprehension is often conceptualized as a process of constructing mental abilities from text through the use of both cognitive skills, such as working memory, information processing, and long term memory retrieval, and metacognitive skills such as monitoring and control strategies for self-regulation of comprehension.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the qualitative approach to find out the real phenomenon under study. It employed the FGD to determine the perceptions of the students on the implementation of the DEAR program. It was conducted at San Isidro College located in Impalambong, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon Province during the Academic Year 2016-2017. It is the first and oldest Catholic Higher Education Institution in the Province of Bukidnon. This Catholic institution is composed of the Integrated Basic Education (IBED), College and the Institute of Technical and Health Related Programs (ITHRP). San Isidro College was founded by the late Fr. Joseph Reith, S.J. in July 1949. He named the school after the town's patron Saint, San Isidro Labrador. The school bears the motto "Ora et Labora" which means prayer and work. This study focused in the college department, specifically the School of Education of San Isidro College.

The participants of the study were the Teacher Education students of San Isidro College enrolled in the Academic Year 2016-2017. Twenty-five Teacher Education students or 20% of the total enrolment of the School of Education were randomly chosen from the master list of the enrollees.

The study used a researcher-made instrument for the research questions. These were all about the perceptions of the students towards the DEAR Program, themselves as readers, their reading preferences, their vocabulary skills, and their comprehension skills. The questions were based on the variables and sub-variables of this research study.

The questions formulated for the FGD were validated by a language expert of the school who has a Doctor in Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Bilingual Education and a Master of Arts (MA) in Teaching English as a Second Language. She was a British Council Fellow at the University of Reading in the United Kingdom in 1991 and a Fulbright Research fellow at San Diego State University in California in 1997.

After validation, a pilot FGD was conducted among the ten Teacher Education students to check on the validity of the questions and also the flow of the session. In addition, the validity of the said questions rest heavily on the subjective opinions of this language expert and students. Second revision

was done, after which the conduct of the FGD was done to three groups of students.

The researchers collected qualitative data from 25 Teacher Education Students through the Focus Group Interview. There were eight students for the second year level, nine students for the third year and eight students for the fourth year. These comprised the three groups for the focus group interview. The participants/respondents of the study were briefed about its objectives and were interviewed in groups by year level. The responses of the respondents were recorded and analyzed qualitatively through audio tape recording and manual taking down of the responses of the students by a Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) student who is skilled in shorthand writing.

Reading groups of ten (10) were formed among students and which comprised a one-session group. This group must be around during their reading session schedule. Hence, this program required students to put significant time and effort to read an article after which they were to accomplish the reading log for each reading task that they have done. These reading logs were kept at the School of Education (SED) office. Moreover, this reading log contained items about vocabulary and comprehension about the reading task that they have done

The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted qualitatively through the coding of the responses of the students. Furthermore, these coded responses were categorized into themes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students' perception on the objectives of the DEAR Program and of themselves as readers

Table 1 shows the summary of the responses of the Teacher Education students on the perceptions of the students of the DEAR program in the context of the objectives of the DEAR program.

It can be gleaned from the Table that majority of the students perceived the DEAR Program has positive impact to them. Fifty-six percent responded to this theme. They further claimed that the DEAR program was helpful to them as students.

Table 1. Summary Responses of the Teacher Education Students on the Objectives of the DEAR Program

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
DEAR has positive impact to them	2.1, 2.2, 2.4, 2.8, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.9, 4.1, 4.3, 4.4	14	56
DEAR is challenging	2.6	1	4
DEAR is appropriate	3.2, 3.3, 3.5, 3.8	4	16
DEAR program is important	4.2, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7	4	16
DEAR need improvement	3.4, 4.8	2	8
Total		25	100

One student's response was, "Very helpful. I learn something from what I am reading and it help in comprehension and vocabulary". Another student's response was, "It's a big impact to me as a student. For me as future teachers, we should be particular in reading."

On the other hand, two students (8%) responded that the DEAR program needs improvement. According to the student, *it's good to have particular time for reading and the writing of the DEAR log after each reading*. From the responses of the students, it can be noted that the students considered that undergoing the DEAR program regardless of the number of years in the SED has positive impact to them and it helped them in their chosen profession.

Reading is undoubtedly a prerequisite of all habits one should acquire or do. It is in reading where one can learn a lot of things, and a vehicle towards achieving success in every endeavor. As Bridges in (2015) pointed out, reading shapes lives; even saves lives. It consider the stories of our greatest leaders across time, culture, and place. Almost all credit reading as an essential force that catapulted them to success.

Table 2 presents the summary responses of students' responses on what does reading or the word 'read' means to them as "readers". The responses were categorized into themes and there are five themes that came out from their responses. Results show that majority of the students' asserts that

reading is a tool or a bridge to learning. Some of the students' responses were the following: "Reading is a vital tool for learning"; and, "Reading means going another discovery of new learning."

The students perceived that reading is a tool to bridge learning. This is answered by 52% of the students as readers themselves. The lowest category, it is on reading helps in pronunciation and reading allows imagination. One student responded like, "Reading is like fantasy, it allows imagination." From the categorized responses of the students, it can be gleaned that students considered reading to play a vital tool towards learning. According to Lai, Tung & Luo (n.d.), students have a need for gaining knowledge through reading because reading is a fundamental and critical skill for students to achieve academic success. If students cannot read well, the door towards the path of learning will most often be closed before them.

Table 3 reveals the summary of responses of the students on the question on what ways has the DEAR Program helped them in their studies. The total responses of the students were categorized into seven ideas or themes. As can be gleaned in the table, majority (48%) of the students claimed that the DEAR program helped them in their vocabulary. Through reading during the DEAR time, they were able to gain more words. As students claimed that, "It helps to discover new words that are not common" and "I gain more words for sentence construction". On the other hand, the lowest there with one student

Table 2. Summary of Students perception of themselves as readers on the meaning of 'Read' or 'Reading'

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Reading is a tool or bridge to learning	2.2, 2.4, 2.5, 2.8, 3.4, 3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.4, 2.9, 3.0, 3.7, 3.9	13	52
Reading is about comprehension	2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 3.1, 3.2	5	20
Reading helps in pronunciation	2.6, 3.8,	2	8
Reading allows imagination	4.3, 4.6	2	8
Reading is a 'sleeping pills' & past time	3.3, 3.5, 3.6	3	12
Total		25	100%

for each category were on, DEAR improves their analysis; it helps their studies; it let them discover more new information and it helps them to be more disciplined.

one student stated, "*I decide for myself, based on my stories. I choose true to life stories and based on facts.*" This implies that the students scan first what the article is all about. If they find it significant to

Table 3. Summary of How DEAR Program helped the students in their studies

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
DEAR helps us to love reading	2.1, 2.2, 3.1, 3.6,4.4	5	20
DEAR Improves/ enhances our vocabulary	2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 4.2, 4.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 2.9, 3.0, 3.9	12	48
DEAR improves our analysis	2.6	1	4
DEAR improves our comprehension	2.7, 3.7, 4.0, 4.1	4	16
DEAR helps us to study	2.8	1	4
DEAR let us discover new information	3.8	1	4
DEAR helps us more disciplined	4.5	1	4
Total		25	100

Looking at the responses of the students, it can be deduced that the students considered the DEAR as helpful to them especially in their studies as well as in their chosen profession. It helps them to love reading as well as it enhances their vocabulary. These responses of the students were aligned to the study of Gallego & Llach (2009) which states that, the relevance of reading as an activity leading to vocabulary acquisition cannot be denied. On the one hand, it provides learners with multiple exposures to words. Apparently, this means that the more one reads, the more one acquires new words. Consequently, these new words that one acquires can be used in constructing sentences in speaking or writing activities.

Reading Preferences of the students

Table 4 shows the summary responses of the students on how they decide on which materials they choose to read during the DEAR time. Out of the responses of the students, they were categorized into eight similar ideas or themes. It can be deduced from the table that majority of the students chose materials based on content for their DEAR time. For example,

them, then they will choose the article to read for the DEAR time.

Students also choose materials that interest them. Many times people are captivated to read on materials and articles that they love to do. These materials are interesting to them that is why they read them. Students have varied interests depending upon the cultural milieu they are in, their peers, their surroundings, their home environment, the knowledge that they have, and many other aspects in their lives.

On the other hand, one student for each idea responded that their choices of the article to read during the DEAR were based on influence, experience, career, faith, curiosity, and mood. This implies that students consider their choice of materials to read base on some aspects of their lives.

Researchers would agree to the fact that students read base on their interests. However, it came out from the responses of the students that it is the content that they will look into first, before choosing the material to read. Reading is usually associated with

Table 4. Summary of Students' Responses on their Reading preferences

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Base on influence by siblings	2.1	1	4
Base on content	2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 3.0,3.9	9	36
Base on experience	2.6	1	4
Base on curiosity	2.5, 2.7, 3.5	3	12
Base on career	2.8	1	4
Base on faith	2.9	1	4
Base on interests	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 4.0,4.1	8	32
Base on mood	3.8	1	4
Total		25	100%

books as only the written words that provide a complete picture of the act of reading. It means that through reading, the individual is able to build and fix things, enjoy stories, discover what others believe and develop ideas or beliefs of their own. Thus, reading provides the key to all forms of information necessary for the day to day survival and growth.

Table 5 reveals the top five choices of students to read during the DEAR time. It came out from the responses of the students that the newspaper was their first choice to read during the DEAR. It can be deduced that the students liked to read non-fiction materials since most of the five choices were all non-fiction materials. From the survey conducted by the researcher on the reading preferences of Teacher Education students of SIC, 63% of the students preferred non-fiction materials to read during the DEAR time. This result was congruent to the findings of the study of Chaudry & Low (2009), where the respondents were asked to indicate three most preferred types of reading material in either print or electronic form. This study revealed significant findings that more than 70% of the participants favored the newspapers among their top three reading

Table 6 shows the summary of responses of the students on the question about the advantages and disadvantages that they see in the implementation of the DEAR program. The total responses of the students were categorized into seven ideas or themes. As can be gleaned in Table 6, majority of the students claimed that the DEAR program was advantageous to them as education students. The highest number of responses was on the category that the DEAR helps them improve and learn with nine students who responded on this. One of the responses of the students was, *“It can help us improve, learn more information that we can apply when we become teachers.”* On one hand, the lowest number of responses of students was on the category on the DEAR helps them in their analysis skills and DEAR helps them became more disciplined.

Table 7 shows the summary of responses of the students on the disadvantages that they see on the implementation of the DEAR. There were five themes that came out from the responses of the students. The highest of which is the area on the DEAR requires time management with 10 students who responded on this. These students considered the

Table 5. Top Five Choices to Read during the DEAR time

Reading Material	Rank
Newspaper	1
Books	2
Magazines	3
Bible	4
Readers' Digest	5

sources. Internet and websites were second in the list, followed closely by fiction and print magazines.

Students' Perceptions on the Advantages and Disadvantages on the Implementation of the DEAR Program

DEAR as it required time management because they have to accomplish the ten DEAR logs, which was one of the requirements in the signing of the semestral clearance at the SED office. Moreover, it is always

Table 6. Summary Responses on the Advantages of the DEAR Program

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
DEAR helps us improve and learn	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 4.8, 4.6	9	36
DEAR helps us in our analysis skills	2.5	1	4
DEAR helps us realize the importance of reading	3.1, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.9	6	24
DEAR improves our vocabulary	3.3, 3.4	2	8
DEAR helps us gain information	3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.9	4	16
DEAR helps us more disciplined	3.2	1	4
DEAR makes us love to learn	4.1, 4.5,	2	8
Total		25	100

Table 7. Summary Responses of the Students on the Disadvantages of the DEAR Program

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
DEAR logs for compliance only	2.1, 2.4, 2.8, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8, 4.3	7	28
DEAR requires time management	2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.7	10	40
On copying of others' DEAR logs	4.1, 4.2	2	8
DEAR seemed a burden	4.4	1	4
DEAR is time consuming	4.5, 4.6	2	8
No response	2.9, 3.0	3	12
Total		25	100%

the case that the students submitted the ten DEAR logs at the end of the semester.

The lowest category among the responses of the students which they considered a disadvantage is on the *DEAR seemed a burden*. This can be associated to the responses of the students that the DEAR requires time management because of the number of logs that is required of them during semestral clearance. They had to fill out the ten DEAR logs in one time just to cope with the requirement of the SED.

Reading remains to be one of the most basic skills over the centuries. It has been one of the focused competencies in the school curriculum and varied enhancement programs have been adopted to reinforce the reading activities in schools. This idea should send a realization to most if not all students that reading is beneficial to them. It is one great opportunity for them to acquire knowledge, and they should not consider it as negative or a burden.

Significance of the DEAR Program on students' comprehension and vocabulary skills

Table 8 presents the answer to the question on what significance do the students think the DEAR has on their skills in English. These skills in English are on reading, writing, speaking and listening. There were two themes that came out of the responses of the students. The result shows that majority of the respondents claimed that the DEAR is significant to them for it improved their vocabulary, speaking,

listening and comprehension skills. One student claimed that: *"When I read articles, I meet new words and add them to my vocabulary"*. The lower theme which the students responded is on the DEAR improved their reading and writing skills, with nine students who responded on this aspect. This result implies that the DEAR has a positive impact among the students.

Comprehension and Vocabulary Skills in English

The narrative reports of students reveal the answers to the question whether they believed that the DEAR program helped them in improving their vocabulary skills. All respondents across all levels answered yes to the question. They considered that the DEAR enhanced or improved their vocabulary skills. According to them, it really improved their vocabulary skills because whenever they will come across a new or difficult word, they will look for its meaning. Consequently, they were able to meet these words and learn the meaning. They used them in constructing sentences and in their essay writing activities.

In addition to the vital importance of vocabulary for success in life, a large vocabulary is more specifically predictive and reflective of high levels of reading achievement. The Report of the National Reading Panel in 2000 for example concluded on the importance of vocabulary knowledge, which has long been recognized in the development of reading skills. As early as 1924, researchers noted that growth in

Table 8. Summary Responses of Students on the Significance of the DEAR on their Comprehension and Vocabulary Skills in English

Responses by Themes	Respondents	Frequency	Percent
DEAR Improved our reading and writing skills	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.8, 3.0, 3.8, 3.9	9	36
DEAR Improved our Vocabulary, writing, listening, speaking and comprehension skills	2.6, 2.7, 2.9, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.4, 4.1, 4.2, 4.4, 4.6, 4.3, 4.5	16	64
Total		25	100%

reading power relies on continuous growth in word knowledge. The relevance of reading as an activity leading to vocabulary acquisition cannot be denied. It provides learners with multiple exposures to words (Llach, 2009).

Moreover, to answer the question whether the DEAR program has helped the students in their comprehension skills, the answer of the respondents across all levels were all in the affirmative. According to the students, it helps their comprehension because they have to pay attention to what they read and make them think deeper. Moreover, students believed that their comprehension skills have improved a lot after going through the DEAR program for at least a year or two.

Comprehension is understanding what is being said or read. When it comes to reading, it is an active process that must be developed when the learner has to become a proficient reader. Effective reading skill development is further accomplished when the learner becomes proficient in literal, inferential and critical comprehensive reading.

Reading comprehension is commonly known as an interactive mental process between the reader's linguistic knowledge, knowledge of the world, and knowledge about a given topic (Rahmani & Sadeghi, 2011). While reading, the reader constructs various representations of the text that are important for comprehension. Moreover, reading is essential for successfully completing all college-level courses. In other words, college students who are more proficient readers are most likely to experience more success in their courses.

During the FGD the students gave suggestions and recommendations for the improvement or enhancement of the DEAR program. Majority of the respondents stated that there could be close monitoring on the submission of the DEAR logs. According to the students, some students submitted logs that lacked the details required of them. They also suggested that students could be given the freedom to choose their own subject/topic/materials to read during the DEAR time and that the students could be provided with the specific schedule, venue of the DEAR time, and the schedule of the DEAR log submission.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The perceptions of the students on the implementation of the DEAR program showed that it has a positive impact to them as future teachers. The students considered the DEAR as a tool for learning that could improve their reading and writing skills. The reading preferences of the students were mostly newspapers, followed by magazines and Reader's Digest. All students considered that the DEAR program helped them in their vocabulary and comprehension skills.

The following recommendations were given: (1) The implementation of the DEAR program will be continued to further improve the reading skills of the students; (2) More reading materials will be provided for the students to read during the DEAR time; (3) A culminating activity will be done every end of the academic year to gauge students' significant gains from the DEAR program; (4) An evaluation will be done about the implementation of the DEAR program.

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